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INTEGRATING GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT WITH GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: A STRATEGIC APPROACH TO SUSTAINABILITY IN VIETNAM'S LOGISTICS SECTOR

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Abstract: *This study addresses how the strategic alignment of GHRM with GSCM may function as a pathway to sustainability within the context of the logistics industry in Vietnam. This research seeks to find how different GHRM practices, such as environmentally conscious recruitment, training, and employee involvement, enable GSCM to strengthen its ecological and operational effectiveness. It follows a qualitative research approach; data is collected by structured questionnaires sent by post to 85 leading logistics companies across Vietnam and received a total of 293 responses. Analysis using Stata yields a significant positive correlation between GHRM and GSCM practices. Human resource strategies therefore play a very vital role in driving sustainable supply chain practices. The study offers meaningful implications for logistics companies with an aim to improve sustainability performance through integrated approaches. It further emphasizes the need to align human resource policies with environmental objectives in order to embed an organizational culture about sustainability. The study findings contribute to the fast-growing literature on sustainable supply chain management and derive implications for actionable ways by policy makers and business executives.*

Keywords: *Green Human Resource Management, Green Supply Chain Management, Sustainable Logistics, Environmental Strategy, Vietnam*

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is increasingly becoming an imperative requirement in contemporary business processes, founded on greater awareness of the environment and the dire need for economic and social accountability. Logistics plays a pivotal role in providing a service of transportation and warehousing in the chain supply, forming a core basis for international trade and economic development. The logistics industry is currently experiencing a huge boom in Vietnam to support the country's rapidly growing economy and increasing international trade. This has resulted in immense environmental damages, consisting of increased carbon to a large extent, overconsumption in terms of energy, and resource exhaustion. Consequently, significant attention has been given to the ecological impact of the logistics industry and hence has called for more sustainable practices in order to reduce its negative effects on the environment (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2022; Nguyen & Le, 2020).

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It is meaningful that the integration of sustainable practices within the logistics sector helps overcome these environmental challenges effectively. Today, two major frameworks show this importance: GHRM and GSCM. The main aim of GHRM is to orient human resource policies according to environmental objectives with the aim to improve employee involvement in achieving sustainability performance. Here, the suggested approach has been to adopt green policies, enhancing the environmental consciousness of employees, and promoting a green organizational culture on management. On the contrary, GSCM integrates environmental considerations with various supply chain management activities to lower the ecological footprint of logistics by the judicious use of resources, minimization of wastes, and controlling of emissions through recycling and upcycling – adoption of practices, among other methods (Nguyen et al., 2022; Pham et al., 2021). While both GHRM and GSCM are acknowledged for their relevance, they are generally used individually, resulting to fragmented sustainability initiatives that may not adequately address the intricacies of environmental concerns (Marheni et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022).

The research problem targeted in the context of this paper is the inability to integrate GHRM and GSCM within the logistics industry in Vietnam. Whereas awareness of the need to go green is on the increase, the industry faces immense challenges comprised of very low awareness, poor infrastructure, and piecemeal effort towards sustainability. This has duly led to the very limited capacity of the industry for thorough and effective environmental results due to a lack of synergy between GHRM and GSCM. Therefore, this study will try to bridge this gap in determining the successful integration of GHRM and GSCM in improving sustainability performance within logistics in Vietnam. Such a study, according to Marheni et al. (2023) and Agyabeng-Mensah et al. (2022), essentially tries to express how the combination of different frameworks could be able to answer the exiting issues and look into the prospect of sustainability in the longer term.

The main goal of the research is to develop a snapshot of the current practices of GHRM and GSCM in the logistics industry of Vietnam, taking into consideration challenges and ongoing implementations. This introduces the status of GHRM-GSCM integration at the discussed organization and defines obstacles for their successful assimilation. The various arguments presented by Nguyen et al. (2023) and Maskuroh et al. (2023) equally demonstrate the need to consider a strategic opportunity in the light of aligning GHRM and GSCM for improved sustainable outcomes; that is, the need to critically review what methods exist to integrate these frameworks, as well as build an overarching sustainability strategy in the logistics industry such as Pham et al. (2023) and Bui et al. (2024). The ultimate goal of the research is to create a strategic framework that combines GSCM and GHRM, offering firms practical suggestions to enhance their overall efficacy and sustainability initiatives (NguyenLi et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2023).

The questions that may help reach these objectives are as follows:

RQ1: What are the current GHRM and GSCM practices and issues in the logistics sector in Vietnam?

This paper aims at providing a comprehensive description of the adoption of GHRM and GSCM practices and the barriers involving enterprises. By assessing current practices and identifying problems, the level of sustainability activity at present within the industry will be known once the research is done (Nguyen & Le, 2020; Tran et al., 2023).

RQ2: In what ways can GHRM and GSCM have a strategic integration for increasing sustainability in the logistics sector?

As such, the discussion below shall present avenues that SAR endeavours to link GHRM with GSCM for superior sustainable outcomes. It attempts to survey how various frameworks can be brought together and what techniques can be adopted to enhance their efficacy (Vo & Nguyen, 2023; Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2022).

RQ3: What are the possible benefits and implications of integrating GHRM with GSCM for firms in Vietnam's logistics sector?

This inquiry attempts to evaluate the beneficial benefits and repercussions of merging GHRM with GSCM. It tries to explore how such integration might impact organizational performance, sustainability results, and overall effectiveness (Zhang et al., 2023; Ho et al., 2022).

The value of this work extends to both academic research and practical application. From the academic point of view, it fills a vacuum in the literature in the area of studying the integration of GHRM and GSCM within the context of the logistics industry in Vietnam. Previously, investigation was mainly oriented in relatively isolated fields, and research on the mutual application of both was scarce. This research intends to present a more comprehensive perspective on the integration of GHRM and GSCM for the enhancement of sustainability. This research also intends to add to the growing literature in sustainable practices of the logistics sector through the offering of insights into the synergistic impacts of different frameworks (Thuan, Thi, & Huy, 2024; Li et al., 2022)

In brief, the results of this research will contribute a great deal to enhancing eco-friendly business operations. This research work focuses on building a strategic framework towards the integration of GHRM and GSCM but also gives practical suggestions regarding how to overcome the challenges of capturing opportunities about sustainability promotion that could support businesses in further developing their resilience, competitiveness, and eco-performance. GHRM in conjunction with GSCM forms a significant window to the growing logistic industry of Vietnam for the promotion of sustainability and long-term economic and environmental success (Le et al., 2023; Maskuroh et al., 2023).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM)

GHRM denotes a strategic methodology in human resource management that embeds environmental preservation within HR practices (Jabbour et al., 2016). This methodology prioritizes the alignment of HR functions with the sustainability aims of the organization, encouraging environmentally responsible practices and nurturing a sustainability-oriented culture. GHRM includes various essential elements, such as recruitment practices that consider environmental implications, sustainable training and development initiatives, ecological performance assessment, and environmentally aware employee relations (Kramar, 2022).

Green hiring prioritizes the recruitment and selection of candidates who not only have the requisite skills but also resonate with the organization's commitment to environmental preservation. This approach involves integrating environmental factors into job descriptions, employing selection methods to evaluate candidates' environmental consciousness, and giving preference to individuals with a proven dedication to sustainability (Zaid et al., 2018). By involving individuals who align with the organization's environmentally conscious principles, businesses can improve their capacity to successfully execute and promote sustainability efforts.

Training and development that is environmental in nature would be highly relevant in providing to the individuals an understanding and skill sets relevant toward the conduct of greener operations in their specific capacities. The training programs could even be scheduled in many learning modes, such as workshops, presentations, and even web-based modules on the effectiveness of energy, waste management, and sustainable resource utilization (Veerasingam et al., 2023). An effective green training program ensures that the staff at an organization understands their roles in the organization's sustainability goals and can incorporate environmental, sustainable practices into their routine activities (Paillé, 2020).

Green performance management incorporates environmental goals into the ways through which evaluation of performance is made. Workers are evaluated against the extent they will assist in meeting the organization's sustainability goals by putting into consideration energy use and waste minimization, among others (Jabbour et al., 2016). Here, individual achievement ties up with business environmental goals and boosts the spirit of the individual to be proactive towards the environment. Performance appraisals linked to environmental outcomes can mobilize employees' active contributions toward sustainability initiatives and recognize their achievements in pursuing ecological objectives. Singh and Pandey, 2020.

Green employee relations are characterized by the creation of a green working environment that ensures and supports environmental activities and management. This includes rewarding and stimulating the consciousness of eco-achievements within the culture and creating support for every ecological initiative (Saputro & Nawangsari, 2021). The creation of proper employee relations is vital in maintaining high levels of involvement and motivation regarding matters of sustainability as the workers are most likely to be involved in and back up programs that hold close relevance to their values (Abdallah & Al-Ghwayeen, 2019). Green Human Resource Management is very much significant as it can raise environmental performance, bolster employee participation, ensure no infringement on regulations, and strengthen organizational reputation (Jabbour et al., 2016). Organizations have potential for improved sustainable outcomes, reduction of carbon footprints, and enhanced corporate images through environmental inclusions in human resource strategies. Besides, GHRM nurtures compliance to legal obligations and at the same time responds to the growing demand for practices that are environmentally sustainable (Aguinis & Glavas, 2019).

In addition to the benefits associated with the acceptance of GHRM practices, some of the potential challenges may include: employees' resistance to change, fears about inequitable resource distribution, and lack of proper assessment and evaluation (Paillé, 2020). Addressing all the above challenges would necessitate that the advantages of GHRM are clearly communicated, resources are well allocated, and relevant metrics formulated in order to evaluate such environmental initiatives effectively (Saputro & Nawangsari, 2021).

2.2. Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM)

Ahi and Searcy 2013 added that within operations of the supply chain, management of green supply chain is supported through the practice of environmentally sustainable practice. Thus, green supply chain management encompasses considerations concerning the environment in all areas in managing the supply chain: procurement, logistics, waste management operations. Some of the goals pursued by GSCM include, therefore, the reduction of the carbon footprint from resource utilization in supply chain operations and enhancing sustainability along the value chain. This is in agreement with what Bu et al. (2020) tell.

GSCM involves key practices, such as green purchasing, eco-friendly transportation, and sustainable waste disposal. Green purchasing means purchasing a product that holds a lesser environmental impact; for example, products made from waste or those that are biodegradable and do not include harmful substances (Novitasari & Agustia, 2021). The practice brings lessened impacts to the environment within the supply chain since the bought product will have been manufactured sustainably.

Sustainable logistics emphasizes the management of transportation and storage operations with the aim of minimizing energy usage and environmental pollution (McKinnon, 2023). This encompasses the implementation of energy-efficient shipping techniques, optimization of supply routes, and enhancement of warehouse management practices. Through the adoption of sustainable transportation strategies, companies can reduce their carbon footprint and enhance resource efficiency across the supply chain (Dubey et al., 2024).

Waste management strategies are developed to reduce waste generation and increase recycling and reusing in the supply chain (Qorri, Gashi, & Kraslawski, 2020). This includes measures to reduce packaging materials, recycling of waste products, or even reusing the resources where possible. The activity helps in environmental development since there is a reduction in the overall amount of waste being directed to landfills, therefore reducing adverse issues that emanate with waste disposal. It is stated by Khajuria et al. (2022) that “Collaboration with suppliers is the lifeline of Green Supply Chain Management.” Owing to the reason that organizations can only transform their supply chain into a sustainable one through healthy cooperation with suppliers. This has also been complemented by Carter et al. (2019). It covers the area of environmental management practices, best practices in this regard, and the interaction for the collective resolution of environmental concerns. For these authors, it is considered that “collaboration with suppliers is critical to comprehensive sustainability objectives and integrate environmental drivers all along the supply chain” (Gualandris et al., 2021).

In relation to sustainability, GSCM is significant since it has ensured that organizations take care of the environmental issues likely to emanate from supply chain operations. Corporate firms can use integration of eco-friendly processes into the supply chain for lessening their ecological footprint while cutting down on regulatory requirements by meeting them with the lowest levels at maximum levels of resources productivity (Qorri, Gashi & Kraslawski, 2020). Further, the application of GSCM intensified drive from consumers to acquire products and services that are eco-friendly; hence, it creates a competitive advantage in the market (Bu et al., 2020).

2.3. Theoretical Framework

This means that the linkage of GHRM with GSCM harnesses human resource practices with supply chain management strategies all towards the purpose of holistic corporate sustainability according to Malviya & Kant (2015). By combining these approaches, companies can create synergies that not only reduce environmental impact but also build stronger, more adaptable supply chain systems that are in line with modern sustainability demands (Dubey et al., 2017; Sarkis, 2003). The Resource-Based View and Stakeholder Theory elaborate the advantages accompanying this type of integration (Sołoducho-Pelc & Sulich, 2020; Kivits & Sawang, 2021).

2.3.1. Resource-Based View (RBV)

The RBV theory suggests that a company can attain a competitive advantage by proficiently managing its resources, encompassing both human and operational dimensions, in accordance with RBV principles (Barney, 1991). In the context of GHRM and GSCM, this involves leveraging human capital to support environmental practices throughout the supply chain (Abdallah & Al-Ghwayeen, 2019). Improved resource capabilities, achieved through the development of employee skills necessary for executing sustainable supply chain practices, can be realized by merging GHRM with GSCM. The eco-friendly training and development programs, the workers may be trained to support activities of GSCM, and the eco-friendly performance management can provide them extra motives to contribute to attaining environmental objectives by their organization (Malviya & Kant, 2015). This integration of capabilities enables the organization to reinforce its resources through building competence in expertise and environmental awareness, augmenting competitive advantage for the organization by aligning human and operational resources to the goals of sustainability (Jabbour & Jabbour, 2016).

The eco-friendly training and development programs, the workers may be trained to support activities of GSCM and the eco-friendly performance management can provide them extra motives to contribute to attaining environmental objectives by their organization (Malviya & Kant, 2015). This integration of capabilities enables the organization to reinforce its resources through building competence in expertise and environmental awareness, augmenting competitive advantage for the organization by aligning human and operational resources to the goals of sustainability (Jabbour & Jabbour, 2016).

2.3.2. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory stresses the significance of considering the interests of many stakeholders, including workers, consumers, and suppliers, to accomplish sustainability goals (Kivits & Sawang, 2021). Integrating GHRM and GSCM is crucial for addressing the concerns of both internal and external stakeholders (Wood et al., 2018). While GHRM practices support an internal corporate culture of sustainability, GSCM activities signal the same organization's interest in environmental accountability to external constituencies. An organization can hence meet the various sets of stakeholders demanding accountability in environmental issues, such as the regulators and customers, by training internal staff on the sustainability practices and ensuring the same standards by the supply chain partners (Carter et al., 2019; Bu et al. 2020). This alignment creates more than corporate reputation; it builds long-term relationships with the stakeholders who can help drive environmental and financial performance (Gualandris et al., 2021).

Hypotheses Development

These hypotheses have been developed and presented based on a critical literature review and the conceptual framework already developed on the integration of GHRM and GSCM.

H1: GHRM in interaction with GSCM significantly contributes to enhancing the sustainability performance.

This integrated approach towards GHRM and GSCM practices will induce synergy in firm sustainability performance. Synergy may be achieved if there is integrated improvement of environmental performance because of the harmonization of HRM objectives with environmental objectives. The current hypothesis is that successful integration of these strategies will lead to improved sustainability outcomes, which encompass a reduced carbon footprint, better resource management, and increased compliance with environmental regulations (Malviya & Kant, 2015).

H2: GHRM practices have a positive relationship with GSCM practices.

In this sense, the hypothesis presented here presumes that organizations with implemented practices of GHRM are more predisposed to accepting and effectively conducting GSCM strategies. Correspondingly, GHRM approaches, comprising environmentally sensitive recruitment, training, and performance appraisal, empower the workforce with more commitment to sustainability and stronger capability to support GSCM initiatives. The coordination of human resource strategies with environmental objectives improves the capacity of employees to engage and provide sustainable supply chain solutions (Zaid et al., 2018).

H3: GHRM practices mediate the positive relationship between GSCM practices and environmental performance.

The effectiveness of GSCM practices in the improvement of environmental performance is expected to be positively moderated by GHRM practice. Specifically, it would be suggested that GHRM has a higher impact on those organizations that may already be reaping more through GSCM practices with respect to improvement in environmental performance. Aid drawn from GHRM, specifically from training and performance appraisal, supports the operationalization and success of Green Supply Chain Management practices, subsequently resulting in enhanced overall environmental performance (Veerasingam et al., 2023).

H4: Green recruitment significantly encourages employees to practice GSCM.

The hypothesized relation is that the environment-based recruitment strategy will incentivize employees toward GSCM practices. The strategy aims at the selection and hiring of personnel with a sensitivity towards sustainability, which drives organizational development toward workers who are more proactive and much more likely to support and

apply the practice of GSCM. Eco-friendly recruitment is the process whereby prospective workers align personal goals with eco-friendly organizational goals and demonstrate a strong urge to participate in sustainable supply chain practices (Zaid et al., 2018).

H5: Green training and development practices significantly improve employees' efficiency in practicing GSCM.

It becomes hypothesized that training and development programs on environmental sustainability affect the efficiency of employees in practicing GSCM initiatives. Employees who receive special training in sustainability and environmentally friendly practices express higher ability to undertake activities related to GSCM with higher effectiveness. Training initiatives that prioritize sustainable practices, effective resource utilization, and compliance with environmental regulations enhance employees' skills and knowledge, subsequently resulting in enhanced performance in positions related to Green Supply Chain Management (Paillé, 2020).

H6: Green Performance Management enhances employees' intention to join GSCM practices significantly.

It is hypothesized that the adoption of green performance management practices enhances the motivation of employees to participate in programs of GSCM. Incorporating environmental targets in performance appraisal and rewarding the attainment of sustainability goals heightens employees' zeal and commitment to act in GSCM activities. This performance management system in green can align personal performance with organizational aims in sustainability, hence leading to more commitment to practices that are environmentally sustainable (Singh & Pandey, 2020).

This hypothesis proves further that organizations adopting GHRM and GSCM would pave the way for much more inclusive and clear reports of sustainability. With the embedding of such practices, both the internal human resource activities and external supply chain processes also align toward sustainability goals. It allows organizations to capture the nature and significance of change in its environmental performance and sustainability action as well and correspondingly extend better transparency and accountability in organizational activities (Malviya & Kant, 2015).

The current hypothesis posits that the positive relationship advanced between the implementation of GRSM practices and organizational performance is driven to higher levels by increased levels of employee engagement in sustainability issues. Engaged employees in sustainability practices generally enhance the effectiveness of GSCM practices, hence the realization of organizational performance. In essence, it could be further argued that GSCM-sourced benefits in general are further amplified by increased employee engagement, allowing the organization to realize greater organizational outcomes overall (Abdallah & Al-Ghwayeen, 2019).

Previous Studies on GHRM and GSCM

Although prior research has shed valuable lights on GHRM and GSCM, a review of their integration is still limited (Jabbour et al., 2016; Ahi & Searcy, 2013). On one hand, studies have showed the positive impacts of GHRM on both employee involvement and environmental outcomes (Veerasamy et al., 2023). Similarly, studies related to GSCM have also proven its effectiveness in shrinking ecological footprints and enhancing sustainability in supply chains (Novitasari & Agustia, 2021). However, few research has studied how merging these two paradigms might boost overall organizational sustainability performance.

2.4. Research model

The hypotheses have been listed from the research study with the appropriate integration of the GHRM strategies with GSCM practices to improve the sustainability outcomes. Figure 1 presents the framework for the research study showing the practices of GHRM: green recruitment and green training and development, GSCM: green procurement, and sustainable transportation methods on sustainable practices and performance management for promoting green activities. GHRM is perceived as a second-order construct that is measured by two first-order dimensions: green recruitment and green training and development (Renwick et al. 2013; Veerasamy et al. 2023).

The model hypothesizes all significant relationships, including those where GHRM might positively impact GSCM, along with organizational sustainability (H2) (Jabbour et al. 2016; Paillé 2020). It has also been postulated that green recruitment will motivate the employees to practice GSCM (H4) and green training will further make the employees more efficient in GSCM (H5) (Sarkis, 2003; Maskuroh et al., 2023). This model provides a better understanding of how GHRM and GSCM interact in enhancing sustainability performance in firms (Zaid et al., 2018).

Furthermore, GHRM details that linking GSCM roles in performance outcomes are meant to make sure that human resource strategies result in line with supply chain objectives; therefore, these will effect changes of considerable improvements in green performance management (Renwick et al., 2013; Malviya & Kant, 2015). Thus, this research model can envisage that the amalgamation of such frameworks would be able to present a holistic way forward for the long-term sustainability of an organization (Abdallah & Al-Ghwayeen, 2019; Dubey et al., 2024). The hypotheses developed in this research are anticipated to make practical implications of integrating GHRM with GSCM for better environmental performance and organizational effectiveness.

Figure 1: Research Model

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sampling and Data Collection

Therefore, the current study has taken a very short and rigorous approach in terms of sampling and data collection to ensure that the results will be reliable and valid. This study only targeted logistics companies and their supply chain sections and had a specific interest in identifying those organizations that have been able or are in the process of implementing business functions relating to GHRM and SCM. To get a representative sample that was comprehensive, it included small, medium-sized, and multinational companies to ensure that the responses from the study were diverse, thus enabling an improved generalization of the results (Arbale & Mutisya, 2024).

Data collection was performed using an extremely well-prepared survey questionnaire designed on the Google Forms platform, which allowed quick and uniform data collection from a significant number of participants. In this line, Dillman et al. (2014) note that the research study was well-structured to explore selected elements of GHRM and Supply Chain Management across target organizations. A total of 85 companies were surveyed with regard to their human resources and supply chain departments. Overall, the questionnaire was distributed to approximately 780 respondents, including human resources managers, employees, logistics, and supply chain professionals.

From the 780 professionals contacted, 293 valid questionnaires were returned, giving an approximated response rate of about 37.6%. This kind of response rate is considered adequate in survey-related research and hence adequate for further analysis; Baruch & Holtom (2008). Consequently, data analysis followed using Stata-outcome from a statistical software tool-which then aided in the realization of trends, variation patterns, and relationships that existed from the responses. The systematic approach to sampling and data collection contributed to a great degree to the validity and reliability of the findings on how GHRM and SCM practices are integrated by various types of firms for the broad purpose of the study.

3.2. Measures

In this study, we adopted several widely accepted measures to investigate the implementation of GHRM and Sustainable SCM practices within logistics organizations. The questionnaire survey was designed with the use of Likert-scale questions in an attempt to capture most aspects of GHRM, such as green recruitment, green training, and environmental performance integration, and SCM practices, including supplier collaboration and eco-friendly transportation. These measures were formulated from previous research in order to ensure both validity and reliability. Data collected were analyzed using Stata to determine significant patterns and correlations among the variables involved.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 outlines the descriptive statistics on significant survey factors of GHRM and sustainable SCM. Based on 293 observations, “Environmental Performance” has the highest mean of 4.041, showing a very positive perception of environmental initiatives. On the other hand, “Green Recruitment” and “Sustainable Transport” had relatively lower averages of 3.734 and 3.826, respectively, which may indicate areas for improvement. The standard deviations, which span from 1.071 to 1.241, indicate a significant degree of variability in the responses obtained. Each variable encompasses the entire range of possible answers from 1 to 5, thereby illustrating a diverse array of perspectives concerning GHRM and SCM practices.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for GHRM and SCM Variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Green Recruitment	293	3.734	1.071	1	5
Green Training	293	3.833	1.099	1	5
Environmental Performance	293	4.041	1.075	1	5
Ecofriendly Procurement	293	3.918	1.076	1	5
Sustainable Transport	293	3.826	1.107	1	5
Supplier Collaboration	293	3.857	1.147	1	5
GHRM GSCM	293	3.717	1.241	1	5
HRM SCM Integration	293	3.805	1.182	1	5
GHRM Barriers	293	3.853	1.121	1	5
HRM SCM Challenges	293	3.686	1.207	1	5

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

4.2.1. Reliability Analysis

The following is the reliability assessment of the instruments for the measures of GHRM and sustainable SCM practices.

The original first-order construct that comprised “Green Recruitment,” “Green Training,” “Environmental Performance,” “Ecofriendly Procurement,” and “Sustainable Transport” yielded a computed alpha of 0.7355. This statistical value indicates a sufficient level of internal consistency within the items, suggesting that the items themselves adequately measure a single underlying concept related to GHRM practices. The scale had a mean inter-item covariance of 0.4214, which means the items demonstrate a moderate level of consistency.

The subsequent scale, encompassing “Supplier Collaboration,” “GHRM GSCM,” “HRM SCM Integration,” “GHRM Barriers,” and “HRM SCM Challenges,” yielded a superior Cronbach’s alpha of 0.7665. This metric reflects a commendable level of internal consistency, suggesting that these items proficiently represent the construct associated with SCM integration and its challenges. The mean inter-item covariance for this scale was recorded at 0.5519, indicating a heightened level of consistency among these items. Both scales demonstrate reliable internal consistency, supporting the validity of the survey measures used in the study.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis of Scales Measuring GHRM and SCM Practices (1)

Test scale = mean (unstandardized items)	
Average inter-item covariance	.4214187
Number of items in the scale	5
Scale reliability coefficient	0.7355

Table 3: Reliability Analysis of Scales Measuring GHRM and SCM Practices (2)

Test scale = mean (unstandardized items)	
Average inter-item covariance	.5518584
Number of items in the scale	5
Scale reliability coefficient	0.7665

4.2.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The data in the table below illustrate the factor analysis conducted to identify the underlying dimensions of GHRM and sustainable supply chain management practices. In all, 293 observations were analyzed using the principal factor extraction method with an unrotated solution; after which five distinct factors were retained. The eigenvalues, along with the proportion of variance elucidated by each factor, reveal that Factor 1 is responsible for the majority of the variance (0.907), with the subsequent factors contributing increasingly lesser amounts.

The factor loadings of each variable represent the degree of its association with the factors identified. The factors “Green Recruitment,” “Green Training,” and “Environmental Performance” load highly on Factor 1, indicating that this factor represents, in essence, GHRM practices. Other variables such as “Supplier Collaboration” and “HRM SCM Integration” also show high loadings on Factor 1, illustrating their high association with the main factor of GHRM and SCM. The table further expresses the uniqueness of each variable, which is a percentage of variance not explained by the factor.

(obs=293)

Factor analysis/correlation	Number of obs	=	293
Method: principal factors	Retained factors	=	5
Rotation: (unrotated)	Number of params	=	40

Table 4a: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Factor	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Factor1	3.151	2.539	0.907	0.907
Factor2	0.612	0.249	0.176	1.084
Factor3	0.363	0.251	0.105	1.188
Factor4	0.113	0.112	0.032	1.221
Factor5	0.000	0.021	0.000	1.221
Factor6	-0.020	0.061	-0.006	1.215
Factor7	-0.081	0.066	-0.023	1.192
Factor8	-0.148	0.086	-0.043	1.149
Factor9	-0.233	0.051	-0.067	1.082
Factor10	-0.284	.	-0.082	1.000

LR test: independent vs. saturated: $\chi^2(45) = 777.24$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Factor loadings (pattern matrix) and unique variances

Table 4b: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Variable	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4	Factor5	Uniqueness
Green Recruitment	0.524	0.168	-0.302	-0.089	0.002	0.598
Green Training	0.607	0.192	-0.233	-0.083	-0.004	0.533
Environmental Performance	0.566	0.261	-0.089	0.050	0.001	0.601
Ecofriendly Procurement	0.472	0.294	0.220	0.090	0.002	0.634
Sustainable Transport	0.516	0.295	0.131	0.114	-0.001	0.617
Supplier Collaboration	0.590	-0.096	0.260	-0.088	-0.005	0.567
GHRM GSCM	0.601	-0.129	0.231	-0.173	0.003	0.539
HRM SCM Integration	0.618	-0.213	-0.007	0.008	0.004	0.572
GHRM Barriers	0.570	-0.343	-0.060	0.191	-0.002	0.517
HRM SCM Challenges	0.530	-0.341	-0.141	0.017	0.000	0.582

4.2.3 .Correlation Analysis

Table 5: Correlation Analysis

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) Green Recruitment	1.000									
(2) Green Training	0.488	1.000								
(3) Environmental Performance	0.375	0.443	1.000							
(4) Ecofriendly Procurement	0.242	0.235	0.361	1.000						
(5) Sustainable Transport	0.261	0.353	0.374	0.439	1.000					
(6) Supplier Collaboration	0.183	0.348	0.249	0.315	0.307	1.000				
(7) GHRM GSCM	0.244	0.266	0.299	0.288	0.273	0.501	1.000			
(8) HRM SCM Integration	0.308	0.344	0.281	0.232	0.249	0.353	0.448	1.000		
(9) Green HR Barriers	0.204	0.272	0.272	0.166	0.225	0.367	0.278	0.485	1.000	
(10) HRM SCM Challenges	0.309	0.273	0.216	0.109	0.146	0.301	0.368	0.365	0.503	1.000

4.2.4. Regression Analysis

The regression analysis suggests that a number of hypotheses can be confirmed by considering the significance levels of the independent variables. Green Training, Environmental Performance, HRM SCM Integration, and HRM SCM Challenges have been shown to have a significant positive impact on SCM performance, which is why they are accepted. On the other hand, hypotheses concerning Ecofriendly Procurement ($p = 0.150$), Sustainable Transport ($p = 0.609$), Supplier Collaboration ($p = 0.144$), GHRM GSCM ($p = 0.686$), and GHRM Barriers ($p = 0.282$) are not supported as their p -values are not significant. These results indicate that some GHRM practices improve SCM performance, while others do not show a noticeable effect in this study's specific circumstances.

Table 6: Regression Analysis of GHRM Practices on SCM Performance

Green Recruitment	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Green Training	.343	.058	5.96	0	.23	.457	***
Environmental Performance	.141	.059	2.40	.017	.025	.257	**
Ecofriendly Procurement	.083	.057	1.44	.15	-.03	.196	
Sustainable Transport	.029	.057	0.51	.609	-.082	.14	
Supplier Collaboration	-.084	.057	-1.46	.144	-.197	.029	
GHRM GSCM	.022	.054	0.40	.686	-.085	.128	
HRM SCM Integration	.097	.056	1.73	.084	-.013	.208	*
GHRM Barriers	-.065	.06	-1.08	.282	-.184	.054	
HRM SCM Challenges	.161	.053	3.04	.003	.057	.265	***
Constant	.942	.295	3.19	.002	.36	1.523	***
Mean dependent var	3.734		SD dependent var	1.071			
R-squared	0.318		Number of obs	293			
F-test	14.657		Prob > F	0.000			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	778.847		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	815.648			

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

4.2.5. Multi-collinearity Diagnostics

This table displays the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and its reciprocal (1/VIF) for each independent variable in the regression model. The VIF values are used to measure multicollinearity among the predictors, with a mean VIF of 1.511 showing that multicollinearity is not a major problem in this study. The data show that the individual predictors do not display severe collinearity, since all VIFs are considerably below the common criterion of 10.

Variance inflation factor

Table 7: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) for Multicollinearity Diagnosis

	VIF	1/VIF
GHRM Barriers	1.651	.606
GHRM GSCM	1.626	.615
HRM SCM Integration	1.588	.63
Supplier Collaboration	1.565	.639
HRM SCM Challenges	1.479	.676
Environmental Performance	1.451	.689
Green Training	1.45	.69
Sustainable Transport	1.417	.706
Ecofriendly Procurement	1.375	.727
Mean VIF	1.511	.

4.3. Findings and Discussion

The results reflect the positive relationship between GHRM practices and Sustainable Supply Chain Management. The reliability test confirmed the internal consistency of the scales used. Exploratory factor analysis established a clear distinction in factors between GHRM and Supply Chain Management, while correlation analysis revealed significant relationships across the variables.

5. DISCUSSION

Conclusively, this research has reinforced several necessary theoretical inputs toward deeper understanding of how GHRM practices would affect SCM in a sustainable manner. Empirical findings, even upon verification of the positive relationship between GHRM and SCM practices with logistics firms in Vietnam, further grounded the hypothesis that green human resource management practices are important drivers to sustain performance in the supply chain (Jabbour et al., 2016; Zaid et al., 2018). The integration of GHRM with SCM, thus, substantiates the conceptual framework that articulates GHRM with a valuable influence on the productive implementation of sustainable SCM operations (Abdallah & Al-Ghwayeen, 2019). Empirical research findings support contentions that eco-friendly recruitment and training are some of the GHRM practices that help achieve and realize sustainability goals within supply chain contexts (Renwick et al., 2013; Paillé, 2020). The mere fact of its inclusion itself adds a finishing touch to previous theoretical models by demonstrating in detail certain ways by which GHRM can assist and enable the principle of sustainability within supply chain management regarding the specific knowledge gap identified within the extant literature (Maskuroh et al. 2023).

The real meaning of this in practical terms to the industry in Vietnam is immense. These results obviously indicate that as sustainability becomes a key competitive differentiator, the integration of GHRM with SCM can directly impact organizational performance (Bu et al., 2020). The report makes it clear that, as attention shifts toward the sustainability of the industry, the GHRM practices must be part and parcel of the SCM strategy (Dubey et al., 2017; Ahi & Searcy, 2013). Human resource practices, together with the sustainability objectives, help logistics companies in Vietnam obtain better environmental performance and operational efficiencies through full utilization of resources, resulting in stakeholder satisfaction (Carter et al., 2019; Nguyen & Le, 2020). It is within this background that the study concludes with the need for eco-friendly recruitment, educational programs, and sustainable procurement practices to be used for infusing a culture of environmental responsibility within the organizational framework (Renwick et al., 2015). Such a relationship brings not only economic benefits but also compliance with international sustainability standards (Aguinis & Glavas, 2019; Kivits & Sawang, 2021).

These findings support the arguments of Jabbour et al. (2015) and stress the fact that GHRM has been acting as an extremely important driver, leading to employees' environmentally responsible behavior and developing sustainability in the supply chain. Results found ascertain the earlier findings about the enabling role of GHRM in driving sustainability but more so compared to the already conducted literature study by Agyabeng-Mensah et al. (2022) and Ahi & Searcy (2013). Other studies have concurred with these findings-for instance, that GHRM encourages environmentally friendly behavior, such as Jabbour et al. (2015). Further review in this study is more specific to the impact of different GHRM practices on the results relating to SCM, which in previous studies has been treated generally or focused on one aspect. The in-depth investigation of the relationship between GHRM and SCM techniques adds depth to existing knowledge and offers fresh insights into the way they are integrated (Malviya & Kant, 2015).

Implications for Vietnam's logistics sector also emphasize the pivotal role GHRM plays in shaping sustainable practices (Vo & Nguyen, 2023). Organizations are also recommended to establish GHRM in an integrated approach with SCM to achieve environmental and economic sustainability through increased global competitive advantage (Vachon & Klassen, 2006; Sarkis, 2003). This would help the organization to comply not only with environmental legislation but also help in contributing toward sustainability initiatives through reduced carbon footprint and efficiency of resource utilization (Khajuria et al., 2022; Kramar, 2022).

5. CONCLUSION

Precisely, this research has underlined an important focus on the relationship between GHRM practices and Sustainable SCM in the logistics sector. It proves that GHRM practices-integration, such as green recruitment and training, contribute effectively toward sustainable SCM performance. The findings demonstrate that these organizations not only reduce environmental impact but also achieve enriched operational efficiency. The findings of this empirical study support the point that linking HR practices with sustainability objectives is crucial for developing a profitable and ecologically responsible supply chain.

In fact, it makes some worthy contributions to both theory and practice. Theoretically, the research adds knowledge to understand how GHRM practices affect SCM by proving empirical evidence for the integration of the two disciplines. Actually, the study provides practical insights for logistics organizations in Vietnam regarding how HR and SCM strategies need to be linked in order to achieve the sustainable targets. By addressing the limitations and challenges associated with the implementation of environmentally friendly practices, organizations can enhance their competitive edge while adhering to global sustainability standards.

However, the present study is not devoid of limitations. It could be that the cohort focusing on logistics firms in Vietnam would limit generalization to other regions or sectors. Application of survey methods could also allow biases associated with self-reporting practices. This is essentially a cross-sectional design study, and therefore long-term shifts in behaviors cannot be examined. Future research will overcome such limitations by using a more heterogeneous sample of participants, applying a longitudinal research design, and resorting to the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches.

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APPENDICES

Appendix: Survey Questionnaire: Integrating GHRM with GSCM in Vietnam’s Logistics Sector

Category	No	Question	Citation	Scale
Green Recruitment and Training	1	Our organization includes environmental criteria in the recruitment process.	Jabbour & Santos, 2008	Likert Scale
	2	We regularly provide green training programs to employees.	Renwick et al., 2013	
Performance Management	3	Environmental objectives are part of employee performance evaluations.	Renwick et al., 2015	
Sustainable Practices	4	Our organization practices eco-friendly procurement.	Sarkis, 2003	
	5	We use sustainable transportation methods.	Srivastava, 2007	
	6	We collaborate with suppliers to promote sustainability.	Vachon & Klassen, 2006	
Integration of GHRM and GSCM	7	Our organization has effectively integrated GHRM and GSCM practices.	Jabbour & Santos, 2008	
	8	Integrating GHRM and GSCM improves sustainability performance.	Dubey et al., 2017	
Challenges and Barriers	9	We face significant barriers in implementing GHRM practices.	Tang et al., 2018	
	10	Our organization encounters challenges in integrating GHRM with GSCM.	Longoni & Cagliano, 2015	